

Supporting Information – Co-folding of Carbohydrate-Protein Complexes

Francesca Peccati^{*,†,‡}

[†]*Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC bioGUNE), Basque Research and
Technology Alliance (BRTA) Bizkaia Technology Park, 48160 Derio, Spain*

[‡]*Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48013 Bilbao, Spain*

E-mail: fpeccati@cicbiogune.es

Phone: +34 946 572 538

Contents

1	Supplementary figures	3
2	Definition of co-folding partners	12
2.1	Proteins	12
2.1.1	Gal3	12
2.1.2	DC-SIGN	12
2.1.3	GspB SLBR	12
2.1.4	Hsa SLBR	12
2.2	Ligands	13
2.2.1	Lactose	13
2.2.2	LacNAc	13
2.2.3	Cellobiose	13
2.2.4	4-deoxy-4-fluorocellobiose	13
2.2.5	2,3,4-deoxy-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose	13
2.2.6	FucOMe	13
2.2.7	ManOMe	13
2.2.8	Histo blood group antigen A type VI	13
2.2.9	sT	13
2.2.10	3'sLn	14
2.2.11	sLe ^C	14
2.2.12	sLe ^X	14
2.2.13	6S-sLe ^X	14
3	Code	14
3.1	Assignment of stereocenters configurations	14
3.2	Root-mean-square deviation calculation	16
3.3	Assignment of ring conformations	20

3.4	Classification of DC-SIGN binding modes	25
3.5	Confidence score analysis	38
3.5.1	AlphaFold3	38
3.5.2	Boltz-2	41

1 Supplementary figures

Figure S 1: A) Distribution of RMSD values for 500 AF3-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-lactose complex, computed relative to the crystallographic structure (PDB ID 3ZSJ). B) Distribution of RMSD values for 500 Bo2-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-lactose complex, computed relative to the same reference structure (PDB ID 3ZSJ). C) Distribution of RMSD values for 500 AF3-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-LacNAc complex, computed with respect to the crystallographic structure (PDB ID 1KJL). D) Distribution of RMSD values for 500 Bo2-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-LacNAc complex, computed with respect to the same reference (PDB ID 1KJL). E) Structural overlay of 500 AF3-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-LacNAc complex. F) Structural overlay of 500 Bo2-predicted co-folded structures of the Gal3-LacNAc complex. Key residues involved in ligand binding are shown as pale cyan sticks.

Figure S 2: A) Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for AF3-predicted co-folded structures of five different ligands bound to Gal3. B) Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for Bo2-predicted co-folded structures of the same five Gal3–ligand complexes. Bars in green correspond to models with correct ligand stereochemistry; red bars indicate models with stereochemical violations.

Figure S 3: A) Overlay of AF3-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the DC-SIGN–FucOME complex, classified into binding modes **B1**, **A 2–3**, and **A 3–2**. B) Overlay of AF3-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the DC-SIGN–ManOME complex, classified into binding modes **B1**, **B2**, **A 3–4**, and **A 4–3**. Ca^{2+} ions are shown as green spheres. FucOME is depicted as red sticks, and ManOME as green sticks.

Figure S 4: A) Overlay of Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the DC-SIGN-FucOMe complex, classified into binding modes **B1** and **A**. B) Overlay of Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the DC-SIGN-ManOMe complex in binding mode **B1**. Ca^{2+} ions are shown as green spheres. FucOMe is depicted as red sticks, and ManOMe as green sticks.

Figure S 5: A) Distribution of distances between the closest exocyclic oxygens of FucOMe and residues Glu354 (shown in red) and Val351 (shown in grey) in AF3- and Bo2-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **B1**. B) Same as A, for AF3-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **A 3-2**. C) Same as A, for AF3- and Bo2-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **A 2-3**.

Figure S 6: A) Distribution of distances between the closest exocyclic oxygens of ManOMe and residues Glu354 (shown in red) and Val351 (shown in grey) in AF3-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **B1**. B) Same as A, for AF3-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **B2**.

Figure S 7: A) Distribution of distances between the closest exocyclic oxygens of ManOMe and residues Glu354 (shown in red) and Val351 (shown in grey) in AF3-predicted co-folded structures classified as binding mode **A 3-4**. B) Same as A, for co-folded structures predicted with AF3 and Bo2, classified as binding mode **A 4-3**.

Figure S 8: A) Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for AF3-predicted co-folded structures of three different ligands bound to DC-SIGN. B) Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for the corresponding Bo2-predicted co-folded structures. Bars in green correspond to models with correct ligand stereochemistry; red bars indicate models with stereochemical violations.

Figure S 9: Overlay of AF3-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the complex between DC-SIGN and the histo blood group antigen A type VI. Glc is shown as blue sticks, Gal and GalNAc as yellow sticks, and Fuc as red sticks. Ca^{2+} ions are depicted as green spheres.

Figure S 10: Side-by-side comparison of GspB and Hsa SLBRs. The key amino acid differences implicated in their distinct glycan selectivities are shown as sticks. The three hyper-variable loops encoding selectivity—CD, EF, and FG—are shown in green, blue, and light brown, respectively.

Figure S 11: A) From left to right: distribution of RMSD values for AF3-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the GspB-sT complex (PDB id 5IUC); the Hsa-sT complex (PDB id 6EFD); and the Hsa-3'sLn complex (PDB id 6X3Q). B) Overlay of AF3-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the Hsa-3'sLn complex. The crystallographic structure (PDB id 6X3Q) is shown in black. A flip in the GlcNAc unit is indicated by a magenta square marking the position of the N-acetyl group in the crystal structure. C) Top: distribution of RMSD values for Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the Hsa-sT complex (PDB id 6EFD). Bottom: distribution of RMSD values for Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the Hsa-3'sLn complex (PDB id 6X3Q). D) Left: overlay of Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the Hsa-sT complex. Right: overlay of Bo2-predicted co-folded structures with correct ligand stereochemistry for the Hsa-3'sLn complex.

Figure S 12: Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for Bo2-predicted co-folded structures of two ligands with the GspB and Hsa SLBRs. Bars in green correspond to structures with correct ligand stereochemistry; red bars indicate stereochemical violations.

2 Definition of co-folding partners

2.1 Proteins

The following protein sequences were used for co-folding. They are provided in a format suitable for AF3 prediction.

2.1.1 Gal3

"sequence":
 "GPYGAPAGPLIVPYNLPLPGGVVPRMLITILGTVKPNANRIALDFQRGNDVAFHFNPRFNENRRRVIVCNTKLDNNWGREERQSVFPFESGKPFKIQVLVEPDHFKVAVNDAHLLQYNHRVKKLNEISKLGISGDIDLTSASYTMI"

2.1.2 DC-SIGN

"sequence":
 "ERLCHPCPWEWTFPQGNCFMSNSQRNWHDSITACKEVGAQLVVIKSAEEQNFLQLQSSRSNRFTWMGLSDLNQEGTWQWVDGSPLLPSFKQYWNRGEPNNVGEEDCAEFSGNGWDDKCNLAKFWICKKSAACSRDE"

2.1.3 GspB SLBR

"sequence":
 "DTERPVVNPSEITVYRGESFEYFATVTDNSNAFDLAKTVVRWLYSNQPRGTEWLQYSVTQVGNQLKVRIFGNVPIDTTIGDYTRYVAVTDAAGNVNATQTEMGNAAVDKTSVNGQFKLIIR"

2.1.4 Hsa SLBR

"sequence":
 "DTEAPQVKSGDYVYRGESFEYAEITDMSGQVNRVIRNVEGGANSTYLSPNWVKYSTENLGRPGNATVQNPLRTRIFGEVPLNEIVNEKSYTRYIVAWDPGNGATQMVNDNANRNGLERFVLTVK"

2.2 Ligands

The following ligands SMILES representation was used for co-folding.

2.2.1 Lactose

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1O
```

2.2.2 LacNAc

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1NC(=O)C
```

2.2.3 Cellobiose

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1O
```

2.2.4 4-deoxy-4-fluorocellobiose

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1F
```

2.2.5 2,3,4-deoxy-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1F
```

2.2.6 FucOMe

```
CO[C@@H]1O[C@H](C)[C@H](O)[C@H]1O
```

2.2.7 ManOMe

```
CO[C@@H]1[C@H](O)[C@H](CO)O
```

2.2.8 Histo blood group antigen A type VI

```
O[C@@H]1O[C@H](CO)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)[C@H]1O
```

2.2.9 sT

```
O[C@@H]1[C@@H](O)[C@H](CO)O
```



```

Map RDKit atom indices -> (PDB atom name, PDB residue name) by reading lines in order.
Assumes RDKit preserves input atom order when using MolFromPDBFile(..., removeHs=False).
"""
meta: Dict[int, Tuple[str, str]] = {}
with open(pdb_file, 'r') as f:
    idx = 0
    for line in f:
        if line.startswith(("ATOM", "HETATM")):
            atom_name = line[12:16].strip()
            res_name = line[17:20].strip()
            meta[idx] = (atom_name, res_name)
            idx += 1
    return meta

def analyze_chiral_centers_with_names(pdb_file: str) -> Dict[str, str]:
    """
    Return {"RES:ATOM": R/S/?} for chiral centers restricted to TARGETS.
    Procedure:
    1) Read PDB without sanitization.
    2) Add explicit H with coordinates (keeps original heavy-atom indices).
    3) Geometry-based assignment of chiral tags from 3D structure.
    4) CIP assignment to obtain R/S labels.
    """
    # 1) Parse PDB
    mol = MolFromPDBFile(pdb_file, sanitize=False, removeHs=False)
    if mol is None:
        raise ValueError(f"RDKit failed to parse {pdb_file}")

    # 2) Add explicit H; addCoords=True generates 3D coords for new H
    mol = Chem.AddHs(mol, addCoords=True)

    # Optional sanitize. PDBs often lack valence/bond order, so keep lenient.
    try:
        Chem.SanitizeMol(mol) # ok if it passes
    except Exception:
        pass # proceed without full sanitization

    # 3) Assign chiral tags from 3D coordinates
    Chem.AssignAtomChiralTagsFromStructure(mol, confId=0, replaceExistingTags=True)

    # 4) CIP R/S assignment
    Chem.AssignStereochemistry(mol, cleanIt=True, force=True, flagPossibleStereoCenters=True)

    # Collect chiral centers. includeUnassigned=True yields '?' where ambiguous.
    chiral_centers = Chem.FindMolChiralCenters(
        mol, includeUnassigned=True, useLegacyImplementation=False
    )

    idx_to_meta = extract_atom_meta(pdb_file)
    out: Dict[str, str] = {}
    for idx, config in chiral_centers:
        # Only consider original heavy atoms. AddHs appends new atoms at the end.
        atom_name, res_name = idx_to_meta.get(idx, (None, None))
        if atom_name is None:
            continue
        if res_name in TARGETS and atom_name in TARGETS[res_name]:

```

```

        out[f"{res_name}:{atom_name}"] = config # 'R', 'S', or '?'
    return out

def process_pdbs_by_atom_name(pdb_files: List[str], output_csv: str) -> pd.DataFrame:
    """
    Process multiple PDBs. Write a CSV with chirality per RES:ATOM,
    restricted to specified TARGETS.
    """
    all_keys = set()
    chiral_data: Dict[str, Dict[str, str]] = {}

    for path in pdb_files:
        fname = os.path.basename(path)
        chirality = analyze_chiral_centers_with_names(path)
        chiral_data[fname] = chirality
        all_keys.update(chirality.keys())

    # Columns limited to target pairs, fixed order
    ordered_labels = [f"{res}:{atom}" for res, atom in ORDERED_KEYS if f"{res}:{atom}" in all_keys]
    rows = []
    for fname, chirality in chiral_data.items():
        row = [fname] + [chirality.get(label, '') for label in ordered_labels]
        rows.append(row)

    columns = ["Filename"] + ordered_labels
    df = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=columns)
    df.to_csv(output_csv, index=False)
    return df

if __name__ == "__main__":
    pdb_files = natsort.natsorted(glob.glob("*.pdb"))
    df = process_pdbs_by_atom_name(pdb_files, "chiral_centers_selected.csv")

```

3.2 Root-mean-square deviation calculation

Root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) of co-folded models from the corresponding crystallographic reference was computed by aligning structures on the $C\alpha$ of the protein and computing the RMSD on the heavy atoms of the ligands. A sample Python3 script for this operation is given here for the Gal3–lactose complex.

```

#!/usr/bin/env python3
"""
compute_rmsd_all.py

Batch RMSD calculation for a target residue identified by the whitespace token
line.split()[3] (supports "4GB" or "OLB" and tokens that include a leading
chain letter like "A4GB" or "B4GB").

Behavior:
- Align each query PDB onto the reference using chain A C-alpha atoms parsed
  with whitespace-splitting.
- Compute RMSD for the intersection of ligand atoms while preserving multiple
  residues that differ by chain. Matching tolerates renumbered residues by

```

ignoring residue sequence number when comparing ligand atoms.
- Output sorted results to rmsd_results.csv with a status column explaining NA.

Usage:

```
python compute_rmsd_all.py reference.pdb [pdb_glob]
"""
from __future__ import annotations
import sys
import glob
import os
import math
import numpy as np
from typing import Dict, Tuple, List, Sequence

# Accept either "4GB" or "OLB" as the target residue name tokens may be prefixed.
TARGET_RESNAME: Sequence[str] = ("4GB", "OLB")
TARGET_CHAIN_FOR_ALIGNMENT = "A"
MIN_CA_MATCH = 3 # minimum matched CA atoms for a valid alignment

def parse_ca_coords(filepath: str, chain: str = TARGET_CHAIN_FOR_ALIGNMENT) -> Dict[str, np.ndarray]:
    """
    Parse CA coordinates using whitespace-splitting.
    Returns mapping: residue_identifier -> np.array([x,y,z]).
    Residue identifier uses the token at index 5 when available (resseq).
    """
    ca: Dict[str, np.ndarray] = {}
    with open(filepath, "r") as fh:
        for line in fh:
            if not (line.startswith("ATOM") or line.startswith("HETATM")):
                continue
            toks = line.split()
            if len(toks) < 9:
                continue
            atomname = toks[2]
            # per original format: residue name is toks[3], chain id toks[4], resseq toks[5]
            chain_id = toks[4].strip() if len(toks) > 4 else ""
            if atomname != "CA":
                continue
            if chain_id != chain:
                continue
            try:
                x = float(toks[6]); y = float(toks[7]); z = float(toks[8])
            except (ValueError, IndexError):
                continue
            resseq = toks[5] if len(toks) > 5 else f"UNK_{toks[1]}"
            ca[resseq] = np.array([x, y, z], dtype=float)
    return ca

def parse_ligand_atoms(filepath: str, target_resname: Sequence[str] = TARGET_RESNAME) -> Dict[str, np.ndarray]:
    """
    Parse atoms belonging to residues whose resname token ends with one of target_resname.
    This accepts tokens like "A4GB" or "B4GB" produced by some renaming scripts.
    Keys include residue token and chain and atom name so different residues on
    different chains are preserved. We intentionally drop resseq from the key to
```

```

tolerate renumbering between reference and query files.
Uses whitespace-splitting; atom name is toks[2], resname token is toks[3],
coords at toks[6..8].
Returns mapping: actualResnameToken_chain_atomname -> np.array([x,y,z]).
"""
atoms: Dict[str, np.ndarray] = {}
with open(filepath, "r") as fh:
    for line in fh:
        if not (line.startswith("ATOM") or line.startswith("HETATM")):
            continue
        toks = line.split()
        if len(toks) < 9:
            continue
        resname_token = toks[3]
        # accept if the resname_token ends with any of the target names (handles 'A4GB' etc.)
        matched = None
        for r in target_resname:
            if resname_token.endswith(r):
                matched = r
                break
        if matched is None:
            continue
        atomname = toks[2]
        # include the actual resname token and chain in the key; drop resseq to allow renumbering
        chain_id = toks[4].strip() if len(toks) > 4 else ""
        key = f"{resname_token}_{chain_id}_{atomname}"
        try:
            x = float(toks[6]); y = float(toks[7]); z = float(toks[8])
        except (ValueError, IndexError):
            continue
        atoms[key] = np.array([x, y, z], dtype=float)
return atoms

def kabsch_alignment(P: np.ndarray, Q: np.ndarray) -> Tuple[np.ndarray, np.ndarray]:
    """
    Compute rotation R and translation t such that P is (R @ Q.T).T + t
    P and Q are Nx3 arrays of corresponding points.
    Returns (R, t).
    """
    assert P.shape == Q.shape and P.ndim == 2 and P.shape[1] == 3
    centroid_P = P.mean(axis=0)
    centroid_Q = Q.mean(axis=0)
    P_centered = P - centroid_P
    Q_centered = Q - centroid_Q
    H = Q_centered.T @ P_centered
    U, S, Vt = np.linalg.svd(H)
    R = Vt.T @ U.T
    if np.linalg.det(R) < 0:
        # reflection detected; correct for proper rotation
        Vt[-1, :] *= -1
        R = Vt.T @ U.T
    t = centroid_P - R @ centroid_Q
    return R, t

```

```

def rmsd_between_points(P: np.ndarray, Q: np.ndarray) -> float:
    """
    RMSD between corresponding rows of P and Q.
    """
    if P.shape != Q.shape or P.size == 0:
        return float("nan")
    diff = P - Q
    return math.sqrt((diff * diff).sum() / P.shape[0])

def compute_rmsd_for_pair(ref_file: str, query_file: str, target_resname: Sequence[str] = TARGET_RESNAME) -> Tuple[float, int, str]:
    """
    Align query_file onto ref_file using chain A CA atoms parsed by whitespace.
    Compute RMSD for atoms of residues in target_resname (any matching name token).
    Return (rmsd or nan, n_atoms_compared, status).
    Status encodes reason for NA when applicable.
    """
    ref_ca = parse_ca_coords(ref_file)
    qry_ca = parse_ca_coords(query_file)

    common_resseq = sorted(set(ref_ca.keys()) & set(qry_ca.keys()))
    if len(common_resseq) < MIN_CA_MATCH:
        return (float("nan"), 0, f"insufficient_CA_matches({len(common_resseq)})")

    P = np.vstack([ref_ca[k] for k in common_resseq]) # reference
    Q = np.vstack([qry_ca[k] for k in common_resseq]) # query

    R, t = kabsch_alignment(P, Q)

    ref_atoms = parse_ligand_atoms(ref_file, target_resname)
    qry_atoms = parse_ligand_atoms(query_file, target_resname)
    # common atom keys now are of the form resnameToken_chain_atomname (resseq excluded)
    common_atoms = sorted(set(ref_atoms.keys()) & set(qry_atoms.keys()))

    if len(common_atoms) == 0:
        return (float("nan"), 0, "no_common_ligand_atoms")

    ref_coords = np.vstack([ref_atoms[a] for a in common_atoms])
    qry_coords = np.vstack([qry_atoms[a] for a in common_atoms])
    # transform query ligand coordinates into reference frame
    qry_coords_transformed = (R @ qry_coords.T).T + t
    rmsd_val = rmsd_between_points(ref_coords, qry_coords_transformed)
    return (rmsd_val, len(common_atoms), f"ok_{len(common_atoms)}")

def main() -> None:
    if len(sys.argv) < 2:
        print("Usage: python compute_rmsd_all.py reference.pdb [pdb_glob]")
        sys.exit(1)
    ref = sys.argv[1]
    pdb_glob = sys.argv[2] if len(sys.argv) > 2 else "*.pdb"

    files = sorted(glob.glob(pdb_glob))
    # ensure absolute paths and include reference if user passed an explicit path not matched by glob
    files = [os.path.abspath(f) for f in files]
    ref = os.path.abspath(ref)

```

```

if ref not in files:
    files.insert(0, ref)
files = [f for f in files if f.lower().endswith(".pdb")]
if ref not in files:
    print(f"Reference file {ref} not found among matched pdbs.")
    sys.exit(1)

results: List[Tuple[str, float, int, str]] = []
for f in files:
    if os.path.abspath(f) == ref:
        continue
    rmsd_val, n_atoms, status = compute_rmsd_for_pair(ref, f)
    results.append((os.path.basename(f), rmsd_val, n_atoms, status))

# sort: finite RMSDs first ascending, then NA entries
def sort_key(item):
    v = item[1]
    return (0 if math.isfinite(v) else 1, v if math.isfinite(v) else float("inf"))
results.sort(key=sort_key)

outname = "rmsd_results.csv"
with open(outname, "w") as out:
    out.write("pdb_name,rmsd_4GB_or_0LB,n_atoms,status\n")
    for name, rmsd_val, n_atoms, status in results:
        if not math.isfinite(rmsd_val):
            out.write(f"{name},NA,{n_atoms},{status}\n")
        else:
            out.write(f"{name},{rmsd_val:.3f},{n_atoms},{status}\n")

print(f"Wrote {outname} with {len(results)} entries.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

3.3 Assignment of ring conformations

Ring conformations were assigned using the Cremer–Pople puckering coordinates with the following Python3 script. Ring conformation assignments for all models are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17618082>.

```

#!/usr/bin/env python3
# assign_ring_conformations.py
"""
Pyranose Cremer{Pople assignment with robust chair labeling.
Supports hexopyranoses (C1{C2{C3{C4{C5{O5} and sialic acid OSA (C2{C3{C4{C5{C6{O6}).

"""

import argparse, csv, glob, gzip, io, os, sys
import numpy as np

```

```

HEX_ORDER = ("C1","C2","C3","C4","C5","O5") # hexopyranose
SIA_ORDER = ("C2","C3","C4","C5","C6","O6") # OSA (Neu5Ac)

# ----- CP core (generic for any 6-atom ring order) -----
def cp_angles_generic(coords6, atoms_dict, ring_order_name):
    """
    coords6: (6,3) array in the chosen ring atom order
    atoms_dict: {atom_name: (occ, xyz)} for the residue
    ring_order_name: string label ('hexopyranose' or 'sialic_pyranose')

    Returns:
        Q, theta_deg [0..180], phi_deg [0..360], z (len 6, in ring order)
    """
    R = np.asarray(coords6, float)
    R -= R.mean(axis=0)

    # Mean plane via SVD
    _, _, vh = np.linalg.svd(R, full_matrices=False)
    n = vh[-1]; n /= np.linalg.norm(n)

    # Align with polygon normal from the ordered ring
    n_poly = np.zeros(3)
    for i in range(6):
        n_poly += np.cross(R[i], R[(i+1) % 6])
    if np.linalg.norm(n_poly) > 1e-12 and np.dot(n, n_poly) < 0:
        n = -n

    # Chirality guard using first, second, and sixth ring atoms:
    A1, A2, A6 = ring_order_name_map[ring_order_name][0], ring_order_name_map[ring_order_name][1], ring_order_name_map[ring_order_name][5]
    a1 = atoms_dict[A1][1]; a2 = atoms_dict[A2][1]; a6 = atoms_dict[A6][1]
    s_chir = float(np.dot(np.cross(a1 - a6, a2 - a1), n))
    if s_chir < 0.0:
        n = -n # flip the plane normal

    # Out-of-plane and CP with final normal
    z = R @ n
    j = np.arange(6); ang = 2*np.pi*j/6
    c, s = np.cos(ang), np.sin(ang)
    fac = 1/np.sqrt(6.0)
    X = fac*np.sum(z*c); Y = fac*np.sum(z*s)
    q2 = float(np.hypot(X, Y))
    phi2 = float(np.arctan2(Y, X))
    q3 = float(fac*np.sum(z*((-1)**j)))
    Q = float(np.hypot(q2, q3))
    theta = float((np.arctan2(q2, q3)) % np.pi)
    phi = float((phi2 + 2*np.pi) % (2*np.pi))

    return Q, float(np.degrees(theta)), float(np.degrees(phi)), z

def classify_theta_bins(theta_deg, phi_deg):
    """Bins matching the user's plotting script."""
    if 0.0 <= theta_deg <= 45.0:
        return "chair", "^4C1"
    if 135.0 <= theta_deg <= 180.0:

```

```

    return "chair", "~1C4"
if 75.0 <= theta_deg <= 105.0:
    ring = phi_deg % 360.0
    if 0 <= ring <= 15 or 345 < ring <= 360: return "boat",      "30B"
    elif 15 < ring <= 45: return "twist-boat","3S1"
    elif 45 < ring <= 75: return "boat",      "B14"
    elif 75 < ring <= 105: return "twist-boat","5S1"
    elif 105 < ring <= 135: return "boat",      "25B"
    elif 135 < ring <= 165: return "twist-boat","2S0"
    elif 165 < ring <= 195: return "boat",      "B30"
    elif 195 < ring <= 225: return "twist-boat","1S3"
    elif 225 < ring <= 255: return "boat",      "14B"
    elif 255 < ring <= 285: return "twist-boat","1S5"
    elif 285 < ring <= 315: return "boat",      "B25"
    elif 315 < ring <= 345: return "twist-boat","0S2"
if (45.0 < theta_deg < 75.0) or (105.0 < theta_deg < 135.0):
    return "twist-boat", "twist-boat"
return "half-chair", "half-chair"

# ----- PDB parsing: resname = line.split()[3] -----
def open_text(path):
    if path.lower().endswith(".gz"):
        with gzip.open(path, "rt", encoding="utf-8", errors="ignore") as fh:
            return fh.read()
    with open(path, "rt", encoding="utf-8", errors="ignore") as fh:
        return fh.read()

def scan_files(patterns=("*.pdb","*.pdb.gz")):
    out = []
    for p in patterns: out.extend(glob.glob(p))
    return sorted(out)

def parse_residues_using_split_resname(text):
    """Return {(model,chain,resseq,icode,resname): {atom: (occ, xyz)}}."""
    residues = {}
    model = 1
    for line in text.splitlines():
        rec = line[:6]
        if rec.startswith("MODEL"):
            try: model = int(line[10:14].strip())
            except: model += 1
            continue
        if rec.startswith("ENDMDL"):
            model += 1; continue
        if not (rec.startswith("ATOM") or rec.startswith("HETATM")):
            continue
        parts = line.split()
        if len(parts) < 4:
            continue
        resname_split = parts[3]
        atom_name = line[12:16].strip()
        chain = line[21].strip() or " "
        resseq = line[22:26].strip()
        icode = line[26].strip()
        try:
            x = float(line[30:38]); y = float(line[38:46]); z = float(line[46:54])

```

```

except ValueError:
    continue
occ_str = line[54:60].strip()
try: occ = float(occ_str) if occ_str else 0.0
except ValueError: occ = 0.0

key = (model, chain, resseq, icode, rename_split)
atoms = residues.setdefault(key, {})
cur = atoms.get(atom_name)
if cur is None or occ >= cur[0]:
    atoms[atom_name] = (occ, np.array([x, y, z], float))
return residues

# ----- ring order selection -----
ring_order_name_map = {
    'hexpyranose': HEX_ORDER,
    'sialic_pyranose': SIA_ORDER,
}

def choose_ring_order(rename_upper, atoms, include_any=False):
    """
    Decide ring order and name for this residue.
    Priority:
    - Explicit: OSA -> sialic_pyranose if atoms present
    - Otherwise hex if present
    - If include_any: try hex, then sialic
    Returns (ring_order_tuple, ring_order_name) or (None, None)
    """
    # explicit mapping
    if rename_upper == "OSA":
        if all(a in atoms for a in SIA_ORDER):
            return SIA_ORDER, 'sialic_pyranose'
        return (None, None)

    # default to hex for common hexoses
    if all(a in atoms for a in HEX_ORDER):
        return HEX_ORDER, 'hexpyranose'

    # include-any fallback: allow sialic ring if present
    if include_any and all(a in atoms for a in SIA_ORDER):
        return SIA_ORDER, 'sialic_pyranose'

    return (None, None)

def collect_coords_in_order(atoms, order):
    coords = []
    for an in order:
        rec = atoms.get(an)
        if rec is None:
            return None
        coords.append(rec[1])
    return np.array(coords, float)

# ----- main -----
def main():
    ap = argparse.ArgumentParser(description="Assign pyranose conformations (hexoses and OSA) with CP + chirality guard.")

```

```

ap.add_argument("--resnames", default=None,
                help="Comma-separated residue names to analyze, e.g. 4GB,OLB,OSA,GLC. Case-insensitive.")
ap.add_argument("--include-any", action="store_true",
                help="Analyze any residue that contains either set of ring atoms.")
ap.add_argument("--output", default="-", help="CSV path or '-' for stdout.")
ap.add_argument("--strict", action="store_true",
                help="Exit nonzero if a target residue lacks required ring atoms.")
args = ap.parse_args()

if not args.include_any and not args.resnames:
    print("Specify --resnames or use --include-any.", file=sys.stderr); sys.exit(2)
target = set()
if args.resnames:
    target = {t.strip().upper() for t in args.resnames.split(",") if t.strip()}

files = scan_files()
if not files:
    print("No PDB files found.", file=sys.stderr); sys.exit(1)

outfh = sys.stdout if args.output == "-" else open(args.output, "w", newline="", encoding="utf-8")
writer = csv.writer(outfh)
# z1..z6 correspond to ring positions 1..6 in 'ring_atom_order'
writer.writerow([
    "pdb_file", "model", "chain", "resname", "res_seq", "icode",
    "ring_type", "ring_atom_order",
    "Q", "Theta_deg", "ring_deg",
    "z1", "z2", "z3", "z4", "z5", "z6",
    "pole_zsign", "family", "label"
])

n_struct=n_res=n_missed=n_filtered=0
for path in files:
    try:
        text = open_text(path); n_struct += 1
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"[WARN] Skipping {path}: {e}", file=sys.stderr); continue

    residues = parse_residues_using_split_resname(text)
    for (model, chain, resseq, icode, resname_split), atoms in residues.items():
        res_up = resname_split.upper()
        if not (args.include_any or res_up in target):
            n_filtered += 1; continue

        ring_order, ring_name = choose_ring_order(res_up, atoms, include_any=args.include_any)
        if ring_order is None:
            n_missed += 1
            msg = f"[WARN] Missing required ring atoms for {resname_split} at {os.path.basename(path)} {model}:{chain}:{resseq}{icode}"
            if args.strict:
                print(msg, file=sys.stderr); sys.exit(3)
            else:
                print(msg, file=sys.stderr); continue

        coords = collect_coords_in_order(atoms, ring_order)
        if coords is None:
            n_missed += 1
            msg = f"[WARN] Incomplete ring for {resname_split} at {os.path.basename(path)} {model}:{chain}:{resseq}{icode}"

```

```

    if args.strict:
        print(msg, file=sys.stderr); sys.exit(3)
    else:
        print(msg, file=sys.stderr); continue

Q, theta_deg, phi_deg, z = cp_angles_generic(coords, atoms, ring_name)
family, label = classify_theta_bins(theta_deg, phi_deg)

if family == "chair":
    pole = label
else:
    z1, z4 = z[0], z[3] # ring positions 1 and 4 in chosen order
    if z4 > 0 and z1 < 0: pole = "~4C1"
    elif z4 < 0 and z1 > 0: pole = "~1C4"
    else: pole = "amb"

writer.writerow([
    os.path.basename(path), model, chain, resname_split, resseq, icode,
    ring_name, "-".join(ring_order),
    f"{Q:.6f}", f"{theta_deg:.3f}", f"{phi_deg:.3f}",
    *(f"{zi:.6f}" for zi in z.tolist()),
    pole, family, label
])
n_res += 1

if outfh is not sys.stdout: outfh.close()
print(f"[INFO] Structures read: {n_struct}", file=sys.stderr)
print(f"[INFO] Residues analyzed: {n_res}", file=sys.stderr)
if n_missed: print(f"[INFO] Residues skipped (missing atoms): {n_missed}", file=sys.stderr)
if n_filtered and args.resnames:
    print(f"[INFO] Residues ignored by name filter: {n_filtered}", file=sys.stderr)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

3.4 Classification of DC-SIGN binding modes

In order to classify FucOMe and ManOMe binding poses with DC-SIGN to modes **B1**, **B2** or **A**, the following pipeline was developed:

1) Identification of the chain id of the Ca^{2+} ion at the primary calcium site. This is necessary as with both co-folding models one specifies the number of calcium ions requested in the structure (three in this case) and they can be distributed differently among the primary and two secondary calcium sites in different co-folded structures requested in the same calculation. Therefore, identification of the carbohydrate-binding calcium is performed based on

a distance analysis from the residues of the coordination sphere using the following Python3 script.

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
import os
import glob
import math
import json

def parse_atom_line(line):
    if not (line.startswith("ATOM") or line.startswith("HETATM")):
        return None
    atom_name = line[12:16].strip()
    altloc = line[16].strip() or ' '
    resname = line[17:20].strip()
    chain = line[21].strip() or ''
    try:
        resseq = int(line[22:26])
    except ValueError:
        return None
    x = float(line[30:38])
    y = float(line[38:46])
    z = float(line[46:54])
    return {
        "atom_name": atom_name,
        "altloc": altloc,
        "resname": resname,
        "chain": chain,
        "resseq": resseq,
        "coord": (x,y,z)
    }

def sqdist(a,b):
    dx,dy,dz = a[0]-b[0], a[1]-b[1], a[2]-b[2]
    return dx*dx+dy*dy+dz*dz

def process_pdb(path):
    atoms = []
    with open(path) as fh:
        for line in fh:
            rec = parse_atom_line(line)
            if rec and rec["altloc"] in (' ', 'A'):
                atoms.append(rec)
    cas = [a for a in atoms if a["resname"]=="CA"]
    cds = [a for a in atoms if a["atom_name"]=="CD" and a["resseq"] in (98,105)]
    if not cas or not cds:
        return None
    best_ca, best_sd = None, float("inf")
    for cd in cds:
        for ca in cas:
            d2 = sqdist(cd["coord"], ca["coord"])
            if d2 < best_sd:
                best_sd = d2
                best_ca = ca
    return best_ca["chain"] if best_ca else None
```

```

def main():
    out = {}
    for pdb in sorted(glob.glob("*.pdb")):
        chain = process_pdb(pdb)
        out[pdb] = chain if chain else "NA"
    with open("closest_ca_chains.json","w") as f:
        json.dump(out,f,indent=2)

if __name__=="__main__":
    main()

```

2) Measurement of key distances to assign the binding pose. This involves identifying the two ligand oxygen atoms closest to the calcium at the primary site and distances of O2, O3, and O4 of the ligand from key residues E347 and E354 using the following Python3 script.

```

#!/usr/bin/env python3
"""
Purpose
-----
The reported distance is now between the
nearest OfA C6 atom and the CD atom of residue number 98 (any chain).
- Process ONLY PDBs present in the supplied Ca-chain mapping JSON.
- Resolve the specific Ca2+ on the mapped chain by proximity to any CD of 98/105.
- Find the two closest OfA oxygen atoms to that Ca.
- Find the closest OfA C6 to any CD atom of residue 98, and report the C6{CD98 distance.

Usage
-----
python analyze_ofA_C6_to_CD98.py ca_chain_map.json [pdb_folder]

Output
-----
closest_ofA_oxygens_and_c6_to_cd98.json
{
  "<pdb_name>": {
    "status": "ok" | "no_ca" | "no_cd105_98" | "no_ofA_0" | "no_cd98" | "no_ofA_C6",
    "ca": {"chain": "X", "resseq": N, "icode": " ", "x": ..., "y": ..., "z": ...} | null,
    "closest_oxygens": [ {01...}, {02...} ],
    "c6_to_cd98": {
      "c6": {"serial": "...", "chain": "Y", "resseq": M, "icode": " "},
      "cd98": {"serial": "...", "chain": "Z", "resseq": 98, "icode": " "},
      "distance_A": 3.141
    } | null
  } | null
}
"""

from __future__ import annotations
import os
import sys
import glob
import json

```

```

import math
from typing import List, Dict, Tuple, Optional

# ----- PDB parsing -----

def _parse_atom_line(line: str):
    if not (line.startswith("ATOM") or line.startswith("HETATM")):
        return None
    try:
        atom_name = line[12:16].strip()
        altloc = (line[16] if len(line) > 16 else " ").strip() or " "
        resname = line[17:20].strip()
        chain = (line[21] if len(line) > 21 else " ").strip()
        resseq_s = line[22:26]
        icode = (line[26] if len(line) > 26 else " ").strip() or " "
        x = float(line[30:38]); y = float(line[38:46]); z = float(line[46:54])
        serial = line[6:11].strip()
        resseq = int(resseq_s)
    except Exception:
        return None
    return {
        "record": line[0:6],
        "serial": serial,
        "atom_name": atom_name,
        "altloc": altloc,
        "resname": resname,
        "chain": chain,
        "resseq": resseq,
        "icode": icode,
        "coord": (x, y, z),
    }

def _keep_altloc(a: dict) -> bool:
    return a["altloc"] in (" ", "A")

def _load_atoms(pdb_path: str) -> List[dict]:
    atoms: List[dict] = []
    with open(pdb_path, "r", encoding="utf-8", errors="ignore") as fh:
        for line in fh:
            if not (line.startswith("ATOM") or line.startswith("HETATM")):
                continue
            a = _parse_atom_line(line)
            if a and _keep_altloc(a):
                atoms.append(a)
    return atoms

# ----- selections -----

def _cd_atoms(atoms: List[dict], targets=(98, 105)) -> List[dict]:
    return [a for a in atoms if a["atom_name"] == "CD" and a["resseq"] in targets]

def _cd98_atoms(atoms: List[dict]) -> List[dict]:
    return [a for a in atoms if a["atom_name"] == "CD" and a["resseq"] == 98]

def _cas_on_chain(atoms: List[dict], chain_id: str) -> List[dict]:
    cid = chain_id or ""

```

```

return [a for a in atoms if a["resname"] == "CA" and (a["chain"] or "") == cid]

def _ofA_oxygens(atoms: List[dict]) -> List[dict]:
    return [a for a in atoms if a["resname"] == "OFA" and a["atom_name"].startswith("O")]

def _ofA_c6_atoms(atoms: List[dict]) -> List[dict]:
    return [a for a in atoms if a["resname"] == "OFA" and a["atom_name"] == "C6"]

# ----- geometry -----

def _sqdist(p: Tuple[float, float, float], q: Tuple[float, float, float]) -> float:
    dx, dy, dz = p[0]-q[0], p[1]-q[1], p[2]-q[2]
    return dx*dx + dy*dy + dz*dz

def _nearest(items: List[dict], ref: Tuple[float, float, float]) -> Optional[Tuple[dict, float]]:
    if not items:
        return None
    best, best_d2 = None, float("inf")
    for it in items:
        d2 = _sqdist(it["coord"], ref)
        if d2 < best_d2:
            best, best_d2 = it, d2
    return best, math.sqrt(best_d2)

def _two_closest(items: List[dict], ref: Tuple[float, float, float]) -> List[Tuple[dict, float]]:
    if not items:
        return []
    scored = [(it, math.sqrt(_sqdist(it["coord"], ref))) for it in items]
    scored.sort(key=lambda t: t[1])
    return scored[:2]

# ----- Ca disambiguation (unchanged) -----

def _select_specific_ca(cas: List[dict], cds_98_105: List[dict]) -> Optional[dict]:
    """
    If multiple Ca2+ on the chain, choose the one with minimal distance to any
    CD atom of residues 98 or 105. Return None if those CDs are absent.
    """
    if not cas or not cds_98_105:
        return None
    best_ca, best_d2 = None, float("inf")
    for ca in cas:
        for cd in cds_98_105:
            d2 = _sqdist(ca["coord"], cd["coord"])
            if d2 < best_d2:
                best_ca, best_d2 = ca, d2
    return best_ca

# ----- per-PDB processing -----

def process_pdb(pdb_path: str, mapped_chain: str) -> Dict:
    atoms = _load_atoms(pdb_path)

    # Resolve Ca as before for oxygen proximity calculation
    cds_98_105 = _cd_atoms(atoms, targets=(98, 105))
    cas = _cas_on_chain(atoms, mapped_chain)

```

```

if not cas:
    return {"status": "no_ca", "ca": None, "closest_oxygens": [], "c6_to_cd98": None}

ca = _select_specific_ca(cas, cds_98_105)
if ca is None:
    return {"status": "no_cd105_98", "ca": None, "closest_oxygens": [], "c6_to_cd98": None}

# Two closest oxygens to the resolved Ca (unchanged)
o_atoms = _ofA_oxygens(atoms)
closest_o = _two_closest(o_atoms, ca["coord"]) if o_atoms else []

# NEW: nearest OfA C6 to ANY CD atom of residue 98 (any chain)
c6_atoms = _ofA_c6_atoms(atoms)
cd98s = _cd98_atoms(atoms)

if not cd98s:
    status = "no_cd98" if closest_o else "no_cd98"
    return {
        "status": status,
        "ca": {
            "chain": ca["chain"], "resseq": ca["resseq"], "icode": ca["icode"],
            "x": ca["coord"][0], "y": ca["coord"][1], "z": ca["coord"][2],
        },
        "closest_oxygens": [
            {
                "serial": at["serial"], "name": at["atom_name"], "chain": at["chain"],
                "resseq": at["resseq"], "icode": at["icode"], "distance_A": round(dist, 3),
            } for at, dist in closest_o
        ],
        "c6_to_cd98": None
    }

if not c6_atoms:
    status = "no_ofA_C6" if o_atoms else "no_ofA_C6"
    return {
        "status": status,
        "ca": {
            "chain": ca["chain"], "resseq": ca["resseq"], "icode": ca["icode"],
            "x": ca["coord"][0], "y": ca["coord"][1], "z": ca["coord"][2],
        },
        "closest_oxygens": [
            {
                "serial": at["serial"], "name": at["atom_name"], "chain": at["chain"],
                "resseq": at["resseq"], "icode": at["icode"], "distance_A": round(dist, 3),
            } for at, dist in closest_o
        ],
        "c6_to_cd98": None
    }

# Choose the C6{CD98 pair with minimal distance
best_pair = None
best_d2 = float("inf")
for c6 in c6_atoms:
    for cd in cd98s:
        d2 = _sqdist(c6["coord"], cd["coord"])

```

```

        if d2 < best_d2:
            best_d2 = d2
            best_pair = (c6, cd)

c6, cd = best_pair
status = "ok"
if not o_atoms:
    status = "no_ofA_0"

result = {
    "status": status,
    "ca": {
        "chain": ca["chain"], "resseq": ca["resseq"], "icode": ca["icode"],
        "x": ca["coord"][0], "y": ca["coord"][1], "z": ca["coord"][2],
    },
    "closest_oxygens": [
        {
            "serial": at["serial"], "name": at["atom_name"], "chain": at["chain"],
            "resseq": at["resseq"], "icode": at["icode"], "distance_A": round(dist, 3),
        } for at, dist in closest_o
    ],
    "c6_to_cd98": {
        "c6": {"serial": c6["serial"], "chain": c6["chain"], "resseq": c6["resseq"], "icode": c6["icode"]},
        "cd98": {"serial": cd["serial"], "chain": cd["chain"], "resseq": cd["resseq"], "icode": cd["icode"]},
        "distance_A": round(math.sqrt(best_d2), 3),
    },
}

# Additional distances: O2/O3 (OfA) to CD(98/105)
o2_atoms = [a for a in o_atoms if a["atom_name"] == "O2"]
o3_atoms = [a for a in o_atoms if a["atom_name"] == "O3"]
cd105s = [a for a in atoms if a["atom_name"] == "CD" and a["resseq"] == 105]

def _dist_to_targets(source_atoms, target_atoms):
    if not source_atoms or not target_atoms:
        return None
    best_d2 = float("inf")
    best_pair = None
    for s in source_atoms:
        for t in target_atoms:
            d2 = _sqdist(s["coord"], t["coord"])
            if d2 < best_d2:
                best_d2 = d2
                best_pair = (s, t)
    if best_pair:
        return {
            "from": {"serial": best_pair[0]["serial"], "atom": best_pair[0]["atom_name"], "chain": best_pair[0]["chain"], "resseq": best_pair[0]["resseq"]},
            "to": {"serial": best_pair[1]["serial"], "atom": best_pair[1]["atom_name"], "chain": best_pair[1]["chain"], "resseq": best_pair[1]["resseq"]},
            "distance_A": round(math.sqrt(best_d2), 3)
        }
    return None

result["o3_to_cd98"] = _dist_to_targets(o3_atoms, cd98s)
result["o3_to_cd105"] = _dist_to_targets(o3_atoms, cd105s)
result["o2_to_cd98"] = _dist_to_targets(o2_atoms, cd98s)
result["o2_to_cd105"] = _dist_to_targets(o2_atoms, cd105s)

```

```

    return result

# ----- main -----

def main():
    if len(sys.argv) < 2:
        print("Usage: python analyze_ofA_C6_to_CD98.py ca_chain_map.json [pdb_folder]", file=sys.stderr)
        sys.exit(2)

    mapping_json = sys.argv[1]
    pdb_folder = sys.argv[2] if len(sys.argv) > 2 else "."

    with open(mapping_json, "r") as f:
        ca_chain_map: Dict[str, str] = json.load(f)

    out: Dict[str, Dict] = {}
    # Only consider PDBs that are keys in the mapping and that physically exist.
    for pdb_name, chain_id in sorted(ca_chain_map.items()):
        pdb_path = os.path.join(pdb_folder, pdb_name)
        if not os.path.isfile(pdb_path):
            continue
        try:
            out[pdb_name] = process_pdb(pdb_path, chain_id or "")
        except Exception as e:
            out[pdb_name] = {
                "status": f"error: {e}",
                "ca": None,
                "closest_oxygens": [],
                "c6_to_cd98": None
            }

    with open("closest_ofA_oxygens_and_critical_distances.json", "w") as fh:
        json.dump(out, fh, indent=2)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

3) Classification into **B1**, **B2** and **A** binding modes using the following Python3 scripts.

FucOMe

```

import os
import shutil
import json

# Load classification data
with open("closest_ofA_oxygens_and_critical_distances.json", "r") as f:
    classification_data = json.load(f)

# Define folders
folders = ["pseudo_B1", "pseudo_B2", "pseudo_A_3_2", "pseudo_A_2_3", "other"]
for folder in folders:
    os.makedirs(folder, exist_ok=True)

```

```

# Helper to extract classification category
def classify_pdb(name, data):
    if name not in data or data[name]["status"] != "ok":
        return "other"

    entry = data[name]
    oxygens = entry.get("closest_oxygens", [])
    if len(oxygens) != 2:
        return "other"

    names = sorted([o["name"] for o in oxygens])
    distances = [o["distance_A"] for o in oxygens]
    c6_cd = entry.get("c6_to_cd98", {}).get("distance_A")

    if names == ["O3", "O4"] and all(d < 2.7 for d in distances):
        if c6_cd is not None:
            return "pseudo_B1" if c6_cd < 5 else "pseudo_B2"

    elif names == ["O2", "O3"] and all(d < 2.7 for d in distances):
        # NEW: classification by O3 vs O2 distance to CD105 and CD98
        o3_cd105 = entry.get("o3_to_cd105", {}).get("distance_A")
        o2_cd105 = entry.get("o2_to_cd105", {}).get("distance_A")
        o3_cd98 = entry.get("o3_to_cd98", {}).get("distance_A")
        o2_cd98 = entry.get("o2_to_cd98", {}).get("distance_A")

        if None in (o3_cd105, o2_cd105, o3_cd98, o2_cd98):
            return "other"

        if o3_cd105 < o2_cd105 and o3_cd98 > o2_cd98:
            return "pseudo_A_2_3"
        else:
            return "pseudo_A_3_2"

    return "other"

# Process files
for filename in os.listdir():
    if filename.startswith("renamed") and filename.endswith(".pdb"):
        category = classify_pdb(filename, classification_data)
        shutil.copy(filename, os.path.join(category, filename)) # or use move() to move instead

print("Classification complete.")

```

ManOMe

```

#!/usr/bin/env python3
"""
Classify PDBs into binding-mode folders using extended distance criteria.

New classes & criteria (applied in this script):
- pseudo_B1:
    * two closest oxygens to Ca are O2 and O3 (order irrelevant)
    * Ca{O2 and Ca{O3 each < 2.7 Å

```

```

* O2{CD(98) < O2{CD(105)
* O3{CD(98) > O3{CD(105)

- pseudo_E2:
* two closest oxygens to Ca are O2 and O3
* Ca{O2 and Ca{O3 each < 2.7 Å
* O2{CD(98) > O2{CD(105)
* O3{CD(98) < O3{CD(105)

- pseudo_A_3_4:
* two closest oxygens to Ca are O3 and O4
* Ca{O3 and Ca{O4 each < 2.7 Å
* O3{CD(98) < O3{CD(105)
* O4{CD(98) > O4{CD(105)

- pseudo_A_4_3:
* two closest oxygens to Ca are O3 and O4
* Ca{O3 and Ca{O4 each < 2.7 Å
* O3{CD(98) > O3{CD(105)
* O4{CD(98) < O4{CD(105)

```

Everything else -> "other"

This script expects a JSON file (the classification data) with distance entries produced by the coordination script. The exact key names used by that JSON can vary slightly (e.g. "ca_to_o2" vs "o2_to_ca" or "cd98_to_o2" vs "o2_to_cd98"). This script will try common variants when looking up distances.

"""

```

import os
import shutil
import json
import math
from typing import Optional

JSON_PATH = "closest_OMA_oxygens_and_critical_distances.json"

THRESH = 2.7 # Å for Ca-O checks

# --- helpers to robustly fetch distance fields from JSON entry ---

def _try_get_dist(entry: dict, key: str) -> Optional[float]:
    """
    Return entry[key]["distance_A"] if present and numeric, else None.
    """
    v = entry.get(key)
    if not v:
        return None
    try:
        d = v.get("distance_A")
        return float(d) if d is not None else None
    except Exception:
        return None

```

```

def get_distance_any(entry: dict, a: str, b: str) -> Optional[float]:
    """
    Try possible key name variants to find a distance between 'a' and 'b'.
    'a' and 'b' should be short lowercase tokens like 'ca', 'o2', 'o3', 'o4', 'cd98', 'cd105'.
    Will try keys like:
        f"{a}_to_{b}", f"{b}_to_{a}"
        f"{a}_to_{b}".replace('-', '_') etc.
    Returns the numeric distance_A or None.
    """
    a_tok = a.lower()
    b_tok = b.lower()

    candidates = [
        f"{a_tok}_to_{b_tok}",
        f"{b_tok}_to_{a_tok}",
        f"{a_tok}_to_{b_tok}".replace("-", "_"),
        f"{b_tok}_to_{a_tok}".replace("-", "_"),
    ]

    # also try variants without numbers spelled: keep as is

    for k in candidates:
        d = _try_get_dist(entry, k)
        if d is not None:
            return d

    # sometimes JSON used cd98_to_o2 vs cd98_to_o2 (same) - handled above
    return None

def safe_lt(a: Optional[float], b: Optional[float]) -> Optional[bool]:
    if a is None or b is None:
        return None
    return a < b

def safe_gt(a: Optional[float], b: Optional[float]) -> Optional[bool]:
    if a is None or b is None:
        return None
    return a > b

# --- main classification logic ---

def classify_pdb(name: str, entry: dict) -> str:
    # require status ok
    if name not in entry or entry[name].get("status") != "ok":
        return "other"

    data = entry[name]

    oxy = data.get("closest_oxygens") or []
    if len(oxy) != 2:
        return "other"

    # collect oxygen names and their Ca distances from the JSON 'closest_oxygens' list
    # closest_oxygens entries usually contain {"name": "O3", "distance_A": 2.4, ...}

```

```

try:
    o1 = oxy[0].get("name", "").strip()
    o2 = oxy[1].get("name", "").strip()
except Exception:
    return "other"

names_set = {o1, o2}

# get Ca->O distances from top-level fields if present (robust to key naming)
ca_o2 = get_distance_any(data, "ca", "o2")
ca_o3 = get_distance_any(data, "ca", "o3")
ca_o4 = get_distance_any(data, "ca", "o4")

# distances between O* and CD98/CD105 (try multiple key styles)
# We'll request O2{CD98 as get_distance_any(data, "o2", "cd98") etc.
o2_cd98 = get_distance_any(data, "o2", "cd98")
o2_cd105 = get_distance_any(data, "o2", "cd105")
o3_cd98 = get_distance_any(data, "o3", "cd98")
o3_cd105 = get_distance_any(data, "o3", "cd105")
o4_cd98 = get_distance_any(data, "o4", "cd98")
o4_cd105 = get_distance_any(data, "o4", "cd105")

# Helper to check both Ca->O distances exist and are < THRESH
def ca_pair_ok(dist_a: Optional[float], dist_b: Optional[float]) -> bool:
    if dist_a is None or dist_b is None:
        return False
    try:
        return (float(dist_a) < THRESH) and (float(dist_b) < THRESH)
    except Exception:
        return False

# pseudo_B1 and pseudo_B2: O2 & O3 closest
if names_set == {"O2", "O3"}:
    if ca_pair_ok(ca_o2, ca_o3):
        # need comparisons:
        # pseudo_B1: O2{CD98 < O2{CD105 AND O3{CD98 > O3{CD105
        cond1 = safe_lt(o2_cd98, o2_cd105)
        cond2 = safe_gt(o3_cd98, o3_cd105)
        if cond1 is True and cond2 is True:
            return "pseudo_B1"
        # pseudo_B2: O2{CD98 > O2{CD105 AND O3{CD98 < O3{CD105
        cond1b = safe_gt(o2_cd98, o2_cd105)
        cond2b = safe_lt(o3_cd98, o3_cd105)
        if cond1b is True and cond2b is True:
            return "pseudo_B2"
        # otherwise not classifiable into these
        return "other"
    else:
        return "other"

# pseudo_A_3_4 and pseudo_A_4_3: O3 & O4 closest
if names_set == {"O3", "O4"}:
    if ca_pair_ok(ca_o3, ca_o4):
        # pseudo_A_3_4: O3{CD98 < O3{CD105 AND O4{CD98 > O4{CD105
        c1 = safe_lt(o3_cd98, o3_cd105)
        c2 = safe_gt(o4_cd98, o4_cd105)

```

```

        if c1 is True and c2 is True:
            return "pseudo_A_3_4"
        # pseudo_A_4_3: O3{CD98 > O3{CD105 AND O4{CD98 < O4{CD105
        c1b = safe_gt(o3_cd98, o3_cd105)
        c2b = safe_lt(o4_cd98, o4_cd105)
        if c1b is True and c2b is True:
            return "pseudo_A_4_3"
        return "other"
    else:
        return "other"

return "other"

def main():
    # load classification JSON
    if not os.path.isfile(JSON_PATH):
        raise SystemExit(f"JSON file not found: {JSON_PATH}")

    with open(JSON_PATH, "r") as fh:
        classification_data = json.load(fh)

    # create folders
    folders = ["pseudo_B1", "pseudo_B2", "pseudo_A_3_4", "pseudo_A_4_3", "other"]
    for folder in folders:
        os.makedirs(folder, exist_ok=True)

    counts = {f: 0 for f in folders}
    processed = 0

    for filename in os.listdir():
        if not (filename.startswith("renamed") and filename.endswith(".pdb")):
            continue
        category = classify_pdb(filename, classification_data)
        dest = os.path.join(category, filename)
        try:
            shutil.copy(filename, dest)
        except Exception:
            # ignore copy errors but still count/classify
            pass
        counts[category] += 1
        processed += 1

    # summary
    print(f"Processed {processed} PDB files.")
    for k in folders:
        print(f" {k}: {counts.get(k, 0)}")
    print("Classification complete.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

3.5 Confidence score analysis

3.5.1 AlphaFold3

Confidence scores (ipTM) for multiple co-folding solutions were extracted from the “summary_confidences” json files generated in an AF3 structure prediction using the following Python3 script.

```
import natsort
import glob
from typing import Optional, Tuple

def parse_file_to_dicts(file_path):
    correct_dict = {}
    wrong_dict = {}

    with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
        next(file) # Skip header line
        for line in file:
            parts = line.strip().split()
            if len(parts) != 2:
                continue # Skip malformed lines
            name, status = parts
            # Remove "renamed_" prefix and ".pdb" suffix
            if name.startswith("renamed_") and name.endswith(".pdb"):
                key = name[len("renamed_):-len(".pdb")]
            else:
                continue # Skip if doesn't match expected format

            if status == "correct":
                correct_dict[key] = ""
            elif status == "wrong":
                wrong_dict[key] = ""

    return correct_dict, wrong_dict

def read_ipTM_and_edge_avg(path: str) -> Tuple[Optional[float], Optional[float]]:
    """
    Read a JSON file in the 'summary_confidences' format and return:
    (ipTM, average_of_off_diagonal_first_last)

    - 'ipTM' is taken from key "ipTM".
    - The off-diagonal average is computed from "chain_pair_ipTM"[0][-1] and
      "chain_pair_ipTM"[-1][0]. If one is missing or null, average the one present.
    If both are missing/null or the matrix is malformed/empty, return None for avg.

    Parameters
    -----
    path : str
        Filesystem path to the JSON file.
    """
```

```

Returns
-----
(iptm, avg) : (Optional[float], Optional[float])
    iptm may be None if absent. avg is None if the relevant entries are missing.
"""
with open(path, "r") as fh:
    d = json.load(fh)

# iptm
iptm_raw = d.get("iptm", None)
try:
    iptm = float(iptm_raw) if iptm_raw is not None else None
except (TypeError, ValueError):
    iptm = None

# chain_pair_iptm matrix
m = d.get("chain_pair_iptm", None)
if not isinstance(m, list) or not m:
    return iptm, None

# Helper to safely extract a numeric cell
def get_cell(i: int, j: int) -> Optional[float]:
    try:
        val = m[i][j]
        return float(val) if val is not None else None
    except (IndexError, TypeError, ValueError):
        return None

first_last = get_cell(0, len(m) - 1)
last_first = get_cell(len(m) - 1, 0)

vals = [v for v in (first_last, last_first) if v is not None]
avg = sum(vals) / len(vals) if vals else None

return iptm, avg

def parse_chirality_file(file_path):
    correct_dict = {}
    wrong_dict = {}

    with open(file_path, 'r') as f:
        next(f) # skip header
        for line in f:
            parts = line.strip().split('\t')
            if len(parts) < 2:
                continue
            filename, status = parts[:2]

            # Remove 'renamed_' prefix and '.pdb' suffix
            if filename.startswith("renamed_") and filename.endswith(".pdb"):
                key = filename[len("renamed_"):-len(".pdb")]
            else:
                continue

            if status == "correct":

```

```

        correct_dict[key] = ""
    elif status == "wrong":
        wrong_dict[key] = ""

    return correct_dict, wrong_dict

correct, wrong = parse_chirality_file("chirality_sort_summary.tsv")

json_files=natsort.natsorted(glob.glob("*/**/*summary_confidences.json"))

for j in json_files:
    basename=j.split("/")[-1].replace("_summary_confidences.json","_model")
    if basename in correct.keys():
        correct[basename]=read_ipm_and_edge_avg(j)
        pass
    elif basename in wrong.keys():
        wrong[basename]=read_ipm_and_edge_avg(j)
    else:
        print("Non trovato")

def save_dicts_to_json(correct_dict, wrong_dict, output_file):
    data = {
        "correct": correct_dict,
        "wrong": wrong_dict
    }
    with open(output_file, 'w') as f:
        json.dump(data, f, indent=4)

save_dicts_to_json(correct, wrong, "chirality_dicts.json")

```

where "chirality_sort_summary.tsv" is a tab-separated file assigning each model as either with correct or incorrect stereochemistry, with the following format:

Filename	Class	0GB:C1	0GB:C2	0GB:C3	0GB:C4	0GB:C5	4GB:C2	4GB:C3	4GB:C4	4GB:C5
4F_cellobiose.pdb	correct	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-100_sample-0_model.pdb	correct	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-100_sample-1_model.pdb	correct	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-100_sample-2_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-100_sample-3_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-100_sample-4_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-10_sample-0_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-10_sample-1_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-10_sample-2_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-10_sample-3_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-10_sample-4_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-11_sample-0_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-11_sample-1_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-11_sample-2_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
renamed_gal3_4fcellobiose_seed-11_sample-3_model.pdb	wrong	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
...										

This file is generated when assigning the stereochemistry of co-folded model as described in Section 3.1.

3.5.2 Boltz-2

Confidence scores (pTM) for multiple co-folding solutions were extracted from the “summary_confidences” json files generated in an Bo2 structure prediction using the following Python3 script.

```
import natsort
import glob
from typing import Optional, Tuple

def parse_file_to_dicts(file_path):
    correct_dict = {}
    wrong_dict = {}

    with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
        next(file) # Skip header line
        for line in file:
            parts = line.strip().split()
            if len(parts) != 2:
                continue # Skip malformed lines
            name, status = parts
            # Remove "renamed_" prefix and ".pdb" suffix
            if name.startswith("renamed_") and name.endswith(".pdb"):
                key = name[len("renamed_"):-len(".pdb")]
            else:
                continue # Skip if doesn't match expected format

            if status == "correct":
                correct_dict[key] = ""
            elif status == "wrong":
                wrong_dict[key] = ""

    return correct_dict, wrong_dict

def read_iptm_and_edge_avg(path: str) -> Tuple[Optional[float], Optional[float]]:
    """
    Read a JSON file, return:
    (iptm, average_of_off_diagonal_first_last)

    - 'iptm' is taken from key "iptm".
    - The off-diagonal average is computed from "pair_chains_iptm"[first][last]
      and "pair_chains_iptm"[last][first], where first=min(chain IDs) and
      last=max(chain IDs). If one is missing, average the one present. If none
      exist, return None for the second value.

    Parameters
    """
```

```

-----
path : str
    Filesystem path to the JSON file.

Returns
-----
(iptm, avg) : (Optional[float], Optional[float])
    iptm may be None if absent. avg is None if the relevant entries are missing.
"""
with open(path, "r") as fh:
    d = json.load(fh)

iptm = d.get("iptm", None)

m = d.get("pair_chains_iptm", {})
if not isinstance(m, dict) or not m:
    return iptm, None

# Chain IDs are stored as strings; convert to ints to find first/last robustly
try:
    chain_ids = sorted(map(int, m.keys()))
except Exception:
    return iptm, None
if not chain_ids:
    return iptm, None

first_id, last_id = chain_ids[0], chain_ids[-1]

def get_cell(i: int, j: int) -> Optional[float]:
    try:
        return float(m[str(i)][str(j)])
    except Exception:
        return None

vals = [v for v in (get_cell(first_id, last_id), get_cell(last_id, first_id)) if v is not None]
avg = sum(vals) / len(vals) if vals else None

return iptm, avg

def parse_chirality_file(file_path):
    correct_dict = {}
    wrong_dict = {}

    with open(file_path, 'r') as f:
        next(f) # skip header
        for line in f:
            parts = line.strip().split('\t')
            if len(parts) < 2:
                continue
            filename, status = parts[:2]

            # Remove 'renamed_' prefix and '.pdb' suffix
            if filename.startswith("renamed_") and filename.endswith(".pdb"):
                key = filename[len("renamed_"):-len(".pdb")]
            else:
                continue

```

```

        if status == "correct":
            correct_dict[key] = ""
        elif status == "wrong":
            wrong_dict[key] = ""

    return correct_dict, wrong_dict

correct, wrong = parse_chirality_file("chirality_sort_summary.tsv")

json_files=natsort.natsorted(glob.glob("**/**/**/confi*.json"))

for j in json_files:
    basename=j.split("/")[-1].replace("confidence_", "").replace(".json", "")
    if basename in correct.keys():
        correct[basename]=read_ipm_and_edge_avg(j)
        pass
    elif basename in wrong.keys():
        wrong[basename]=read_ipm_and_edge_avg(j)
    else:
        print("Non trovato")

def save_dicts_to_json(correct_dict, wrong_dict, output_file):
    data = {
        "correct": correct_dict,
        "wrong": wrong_dict
    }
    with open(output_file, 'w') as f:
        json.dump(data, f, indent=4)

save_dicts_to_json(correct, wrong, "chirality_dicts.json")

```

where "chirality_sort_summary.tsv" is the same file described in the previous section.